

Remediation of groundwater polluted with HCHs using solar light irradiation

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INTRODUCTION

During the 20th century, lindane (γ -hexachlorocyclohexane, HCH, $C_6H_6Cl_6$) was a pesticide produced and marketed worldwide. The synthesis of this compound was carried out with benzene and chlorine under UV irradiation [1]. In 2008, the European Union forbade the production of lindane because it was classified as a carcinogenic compound by the International Agency for Research on Cancer. Despite this, uncontrolled industrial landfills still exist where chemical companies dumped tonnes of lindane and other isomers of HCH over the years, causing soil and groundwater pollution by leaching [2]. In Spain, two landfills in the Aragón region (northeast of Spain) are highly contaminated by lindane production wastes (Bailín and Sardas). For this reason, it is necessary to develop clean and efficient technologies that allow the removal of HCH isomers (HCHs) from water bodies.

Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs) emerge as an efficient and environmentally friendly alternative for degrading organic pollutants in water bodies [3]. These processes are based on producing large amounts of free radicals that can attack the pollutants, favouring their degradation and even their complete mineralization. The use of light irradiation under specific operating conditions can promote the production of free radicals, although the energy requirements can compromise the implementation of the technology. To overcome this limitation, the application of direct sunlight has been proposed in recent years as a cost-free and renewable light source. With this background, the main aim of the present work is to evaluate the degradation of HCHs in the aqueous phase using sunlight-activated persulfate in the presence of ferrioxalate as the catalyst.

EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

Figure 1. Photograph of the photo-reactor and solar simulator: (1) flat plate photoreactor, (2) lamp housing, (3) collimator, (4) air mass and water filters, (5) input, and (6) output of the reactive solution from the recirculation tank [4].

Figure 2. CPC solar reactor.

RESULTS

Figure 3. Conversion of HCHs as function of the operation time during the photo-oxidation of synthetic groundwater saturated with HCHs using a solar simulator. (a) α -HCH; (b) β -HCH; (c) γ -HCH; (d) δ -HCH; (\square) $[Fe]_0$: 1 mg dm^{-3} ; (\blacksquare) $[Fe]_0$: 3.5 mg dm^{-3} ; (\bullet) $[Fe]_0$: 7 mg dm^{-3} ; $[Na_2S_2O_8]_0$: 100 mg dm^{-3} ; q_w : $1.12 \cdot 10^{-7}$ E $cm^{-2} s^{-1}$. Onset: total conversion of HCHs as function of the catalyst dosage.

- ✓ Elimination of more than **50 %** of HCHs with the solar simulator. α - and γ -HCH reach final conversions of around **80 %**. These isomers present more chlorine atoms in axial position than β - and δ -HCH.
- ✓ No significant influence of the catalyst (iron) on the degradation of HCHs.

Figure 4. Conversion of HCHs as function of the operation time during the photo-oxidation of synthetic and real groundwater saturated with HCHs using a CPC reactor. (a) α -HCH; (b) β -HCH; (c) γ -HCH; (d) δ -HCH; (\square) synthetic groundwater; (\blacksquare) real groundwater; $[Na_2S_2O_8]_0$: 500 mg dm^{-3} ; $[Fe]_0$: 3.5 mg dm^{-3} ; q_w : $8.60 \cdot 10^{-8}$ E $cm^{-2} s^{-1}$.

- ✓ **Complete elimination** of HCHs in synthetic groundwater with the CPC solar reactor using 500 mg dm^{-3} persulfate.
- ✓ **Real groundwater** contains inorganic ions and natural organic matter that compete with the degradation of HCHs. This suggests that **higher oxidant dosages** should be used.

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